

Online Assessment and its Implications for Education Quality (A Case Study in Banyumas)

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ABSTRACT

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The pandemic situation has changed aspects of education. Online learning and assessment are still an alternative solution. However, there are still pros and cons related to online assessment activities. This is because online evaluation activities cannot be carried out optimally according to standard norms. This research aimed to: (1) analyze the online assessment type, (2) analyze the planning and implementation process of online assessment, (3) analyze the criteria in determining student achievement, and (4) determine the implications of online assessment for the quality of education. This research is qualitative research, which investigates the natural conditions of an object for which the researcher is the key instrument, and the results focus more on generalization. Data collection was carried out through observation, interviews, and documentation. Data analysis is carried out interactively and continuously until the data is saturated. The results show that (1) the types of assessment used in the assessment are multiple choice, essay, practical test, and oral test, (2) the assessment planning process consists of three stages; the media are Google form and WhatsApp, some of the assessment frequency remains the same and some are less frequent, while the obstacle in assessment is waiting for parents' cellphones, (3) some learning assessment criteria remain the same and some provide added value for those who submit on time, and (4) The implication of online learning assessment is that the average ability decreases (for example in reading, writing, and arithmetic), behavior also decline.

KEYWORDS:

Implication, Online assessment, Pandemic

INTRODUCTION

The pandemic situation has changed aspects of education. Online learning and assessment are still an alternative solution. However, there are still pros and cons related to online assessment activities. This is because online evaluation activities cannot be carried out optimally according to standard norms. Formal evaluation techniques can be carried out, but the value of objectivity and evaluation principles cannot be applied, because there are many obstacles. The evaluation process did not run as expected.

Research carried out by Hani Subakti, Gamar Al Haddar, Elizabeth Angela Orin, Analysis of Curriculum 2013 Skills Assessment in Online Learning for Elementary

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School, showed that an assessment of practical skills has been carried out for children through singing assignments that are videoed and photographing the work sent via WhatsApp (Subakti et al., 2021). Meanwhile, project and portfolio skills cannot be carried out due to technical difficulties (Subakti et al., 2021). Another research was conducted by Zuliyanti, Denny and Muhsinin, Umil and Azir, Muhammad (2021), concluded that the online learning outcomes assessment process which includes the cognitive domain, affective domain and psychomotor domain can run well because it is carried out directly during the learning process via the Zoom and WhatsApp applications. However, the implementation of the evaluation experienced obstacles, related to signals and time constraints. Thus, even though the implementation of the evaluation can run, it is not possible to get accurate results.

Regarding student attitudes, research by Eryuni Ramdhayani and Wiwi Noviati shows that assessing student behavior during the pandemic is difficult and does not produce valid results as expected. This is because teachers can only see students' responses when carrying out

assignments from the teacher. In the future, assessment of student attitudes and behavior needs to be improved, starting from planning, preparing assessment instruments, as well as the online learning process (Eryuni Ramdhayani et al., 2020). Besides, Kharisma Nur Malinda Sari (2021) found that authentic assessment of learning carried out online is difficult to carry out optimally because it turns out that the learning that takes place conveys more knowledge material than attitudes and skills. This can be seen from the use of Moodle e-learning at Tanjungpura University, e-learning at IAIN Pontianak, Google Classroom, and Edmodo in various schools in Pontianak mostly focus more on assessing final grades from the knowledge aspect without any aspects of students' attitudes.

Gilbert, Angel Chynora (2021) conducted research with the title "Implementation of Assessment of Students' Social Attitudes in Online Learning (Study at UPT SMAN 13 Bone). The research results showed that the assessment of students' attitudes was carried out online by self-assessment via Google Form and online observation. Collaboration with other teachers such as subject teachers and guidance counselors. The assessment went relatively well. The obstacle faced is the lack of frequency of communication between teachers, students, and parents, so that data on students' attitude development is not obtained completely.

From research to assess the implementation of the 2013 curriculum in online learning during the Covid19 pandemic at SDN Bintoro 5, Demak Regency, Masrokhah found that the value of implementing the 2013 curriculum in online learning during the Covid19 pandemic at SDN Bintoro 5, Demak Regency, was an average of 60% overall in the category " Good". Of the four aspects evaluated, the highest evaluation results for the process and learning outcomes evaluation aspects were 75% in the "good" category. Even though the lowest score was in the aspect of learning planning and obstacles, 54% was in the "fairly good" category (Masrokhah, 2020).

The results of research by Astuti & Kismimi (2021) with the topic "Implementation of authentic assessment during the Covid19 pandemic on the subject of sociology of social problems in society at SMA Negeri 1 Godong" shows that the implementation of authentic assessment during the Covid19 pandemic Sociology in SMA Negeri 1 Godong does not work according to authentic assessment standards. Barriers to authentic assessment are teachers having difficulty following online distance learning assessments and students having difficulty accessing online learning applications. Teachers attempt to overcome barriers to

authentic assessment by motivating them to learn, discussing effective online assessment with other teachers, and participating in teacher development training courses.

Maryani, K. (2020), researched "Assessment and Reporting of Children's Development During Home Learning During the Covid-19 Pandemic" and produced findings that during the pandemic teachers experienced difficulties in assessing and reporting the development and progress of students' competencies due to lack of there is maximum cooperation with parents to provide stimulus and motivation as well as report on the child's progress while at home. With conditions like this, it is felt necessary to provide insight into knowledge about how to assess and report children when studying at home through a seminar. From the seminar, it is hoped that there will be recommendations on various alternative ways to assess and report children's development at home and how to collaborate well with parents as teacher partners in educating children.

From the description, the objectives of this research are to: (1) find out and analyze the teacher assessment evaluation model during the pandemic, (2) find out and analyze the process of planning and implementing assessments carried out by teachers, (3) analyze the criteria in determining success, and (4) knowing the implications of online learning assessment for the quality of education.

METHOD

Research Design

The research is qualitative research. The qualitative research method is a research method based on the philosophy of postpositivism. Qualitative research methods are used to examine the natural condition of objects where the researcher is the key instrument whose results focus more on generalization (Sugiyono, 2015). The research approach in this research is a Grounded Theory approach. Grounded Theory is a qualitative research approach used to create theories that explain problems at a broad conceptual level, processes, actions, or interactions on substantive topics (Creswell, 2009).

Participant

Participants in this research were teachers and students from several schools in Banyumas sub-district. The selected schools represent two different geographic locations (downtown and countryside). This research involved 3 teachers from the city center and 4 teachers from the suburbs, as well as 9 students from the city center and 6 from the suburbs. The list of participants in this study is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Research Respondent

No.	Respondent	Role	School Geographical Location	No.	Respondent	Role	School Geographical Location
1.	NYN	Teacher	City center	12.	NR	Student	City center
2.	SNW	Teacher	City center	13.	LSK	Student	City center
3.	SDK	Teacher	City center	14.	AND	Student	City center
4.	AZM	Teacher	Suburbs	15.	SNN	Student	City center
5.	SDY	Teacher	Suburbs	16.	MIR	Student	City center
6.	WAS	Teacher	Suburbs	17.	HRR	Student	Suburbs
7.	YSR	Teacher	Suburbs	18.	GIS	Student	Suburbs
8.	MIR	Student	City center	19.	WAH	Student	Suburbs
9.	SAP	Student	City center	20.	MAS	Student	Suburbs
10.	KYK	Student	City center	21.	ASY	Student	Suburbs
11.	ZPN	Student	City center	22.	SKM	Student	Suburbs

Material

The data collection techniques used in this research are observation, interviews, and documentation. Interviews in the research were used to explore the steps and forms of online learning assessment, the assessment criteria used, and the implications of assessment for the quality of education during the pandemic in elementary schools in the Banyumas District area. Observations were made on the process of planning and implementing assessments by teachers in online learning. Meanwhile, documentation in this research is devoted to collecting data that has not been recorded through observation and interviews.

Procedure

The research was conducted by interviewing teachers regarding the online assessment process and its implications. To complete this information, continue with observations about the assessment implementation process. Meanwhile, students were also interviewed to obtain data about online assessments from the student's perspective.

Data Analysis

Data analysis is carried out to systematically search for and organize data obtained from interviews, field notes and other materials, so that it is easy to understand, and the findings can be informed to others (Bogdan & Bikien, 1998). Activities in qualitative data analysis are carried out interactively and continuously until the data is saturated (Miles & Huberman, 2002). Activities in data analysis consist of data reduction, data display, and drawing conclusion/verification.

Apart from using these techniques, this research also uses qualitative data analysis techniques using coding. Coding is the activity of providing code to important information in data. A code is a word or short phrase that summarizes, highlights a message, or captures the essence of the data. In simple terms, a code is a word or short phrase that has the essence of a segment of data (Saldana, 2009).

Data validity techniques are an effort to check the accuracy of qualitative research results by applying certain procedures. There are 3 types of data validity techniques,

namely triangulation, member checking, and external auditing (Creswell, 2009). The data validity technique taken in this research is triangulation. Triangulation consists of 3 types, namely time triangulation, source triangulation, and technical triangulation (Sugiyono, 2015). This research uses source triangulation and technique triangulation. Source triangulation in this research is a procedure of comparing data from 1 teacher with other teachers and data from 1 student with other students. Meanwhile, technical triangulation in this research is a procedure for comparing data resulting from observation techniques, interview techniques and documentation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The research results will be described as follows.

Types of Online Assessment of Student Learning Outcomes at Elementary Schools

Data from the 7 teachers who were respondents in this study showed that the types of assessment used in evaluating student learning outcomes at elementary school consisted of (1) oral test, (2) practice test, (3) multiple choice, and (4) essay. This is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Teacher Assessment Type

Respondents who carried out this type of oral assessment were WAS, SNW, AZM, and SDY. WAS, SNW, AZM, and SDY. They ask students to send photos and videos for practical or oral assessments and send photos of answer sheets for written assessments via WhatsApp.

Assessments via oral and practical tests via video were also carried out by YSR via WhatsApp, but written assessments were carried out via Google Form. Subjects YSR, SDK, and NYN stated that Google forms were used to carry out multiple choice and essays. This statement is also supported by the statements of SNN and WAH. The teacher asks them to send product photos (for example in fine arts practice assessments) and videos of memorizing Quran verses (religious learning).

The learning process is an effort to change student behavior to lead to progress. For this reason, every human behavior always undergoes a process of assessment, measurement, and appraisal. In the learning process at school, students also carry out an evaluation process. Assessment or evaluation is an activity of collecting information in various ways to monitor student development and performance. In terms of function, assessment is divided into 3 types including: (1) diagnostic assessment, (2) formative assessment, and (3) summative assessment. Diagnostic assessment is a form of pre-assessment, where a teacher makes efforts to understand students' strengths and weaknesses before carrying out the learning process (Leeflang & Allerberger, 2019). This assessment allows teachers to find out the cognitive level of students so they can decide on follow-up actions in designing learning. Formative assessment is an evaluation carried out by the teacher during the learning process (Tamah & Wirjawan, 2019). Formative assessment is usually called Assessment for Learning (AFL). Meanwhile, summative assessment is an assessment carried out at the end of the learning process (Ibrahim & Ishartiwi, 2017). Summative assessment is usually used to determine students' final performance such as end-of-semester tests or graduation exams. Summative assessment is usually called Assessment of Learning (AOF).

Meanwhile, in terms of assessment types, there are 4 types of assessment including: (1) written assessment, (2) practical assessment, (3) product assessment, (4) project assessment, (5) portfolio assessment, (6) self-assessment, and (7) assessment between friends. Written assessments are often carried out in almost every level school, even in universities there are also these types of assessments (Marathe et al., 2020). Students are tested on their abilities regarding the lessons they have studied for one semester, or once a week. Teachers can get various information about their students' abilities with this test. So, teachers can also evaluate what needs to be improved so that their students will be even better. As time progressed, written tests initially used writing tools, such as paper, pens, pencils, erasers, rulers, etc. Now we use modern tools such as computers online. So, it will be easier for students to take this test and the time used more efficiently. It's not just students who find it easier to test in this digital age, of course teachers also find it easier. He doesn't need to scribble on paper to assess the results, he just needs to open the computer and open the data that the students have

worked on to assess it. In fact, in the future, perhaps this written test will be even more sophisticated.

Practical assessment is an assessment that requires a response in the form of skills to carry out an activity in accordance with competency expected (Stadnik, 2021). Thus, the aspect assessed in the practical assessment is the quality of the process of doing or performing a task. Practical assessment aims to assess students' ability to demonstrate their skills in carrying out an activity. Practical assessment is more authentic than paper and pencil assessment because the forms of the tasks better represent the abilities needed in daily life practice.

Product assessment is an assessment of students' skills in applying the knowledge they have into a product within a certain time in accordance with predetermined criteria both in terms of process and final results (Rahman et al., 2019). Product assessment is carried out on the quality of a product produced. Product assessment aims to (1) assess students' skills in making certain products in relation to achieving learning objectives in class, (2) assess mastery of skills as a requirement for learning the next skill, and (3) assess students' ability to explore and develop ideas in design and demonstrate innovation and creation.

Project assessment is an activity to determine students' abilities to put their knowledge into practice through completing a project within a certain period/time (Bartolomé & Benítez, 2022). Project assessment can be carried out to assess one or more basic competencies in one or more subjects. The instrument is a series of activities starting from planning, data collection, data organization, data processing and presentation, and reporting. Project assessment aims to develop and monitor students' skills in planning, investigating, and analyzing projects. In this context students can demonstrate their experience and knowledge about a topic, formulate questions and investigate the topic through reading, tours, and interviews. Their activities can then be used to assess their ability to work alone or in groups. The product of a project can be used to assess students' ability to communicate their findings in an appropriate form, for example presenting results through visual displays or written reports.

The next assessment is a portfolio assessment. This assessment usually requires teachers to collect their notes during a particular learning process (Anggreni et al., 2020). Then the teacher can assess them from these notes. Then the teacher evaluates them to become even better. So, they can get good grades and graduate on time.

Self-assessment is an assessment where the teacher asks students to assess themselves (Andrade, 2019). The way teachers ask students to reveal what they know about themselves honestly. For example, students reveal something they have, whether it is a weakness or an advantage. Then this is recorded by the teacher for future evaluation of the student. In this way, teachers can assess and understand their students in depth. Of course, this must

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be done one by one, not as a whole. Because usually there are some students who are embarrassed to reveal themselves when in a crowded situation. It's different if the situation is quiet or there is only one eye to eye, the student will not hesitate to reveal himself. So, for an assessment like this, the teacher must be clever in seeing the situation and condition of his students.

Assessments between friends are the same as assessments of oneself (Double et al., 2020). However, the differentiates the assessment between friends who express it is the friend himself. So, students must get to know each other more deeply. So, they can reveal the characteristics of other students to their teachers. And teachers also get information from their students more easily. The advantage of this assessment is that students will get to know each other better. Because they are required to be able to reveal the characteristics of their friends in that class. If he doesn't want to make friends with other students, he won't be able to get this peer-to-peer assessment. And of course, in this assessment the teacher must also be able to guide his students. Don't let all the disgrace of each student be exposed. Likewise with some secrets that should not be revealed in public. So, teachers must be very clever in guiding their students when speaking about their friends so as not to make their names bad.

Even though there are 7 types of assessments, the Covid-19 pandemic means that several types of assessments cannot be carried out. For example, assessment between friends, this assessment requires interaction between one student and other students. During the Covid-19 Pandemic, direct human interaction was very limited. Creating interaction between students virtually during the Covid-19 pandemic is very difficult. This makes this type of assessment very difficult to implement during the Covid-19 pandemic. From the results of the assessment data, elementary school teacher respondents in the Banyumas District used assessment types including (1) oral, (2) multiple choice, (3) practice, and (4) description. These four types of assessments were assessments that were very commonly used in the pre-pandemic era. This means that the Covid-19 pandemic does not have a significant impact on the type of teacher assessment.

The Process of Online Assessment of Student Learning Outcomes during the Covid-19 Pandemic

The results on assessment process of student learning outcomes during the Covid-19 pandemic show 3 findings, including: (1) the assessment media used by teachers, (2) the frequency of assessments carried out by teachers, and (3) obstacles in online assessment.

Assessment media is a tool used by teachers to carry out assessments during the Covid-19 Pandemic. The assessment media used by teachers consists of Google Form and WhatsApp. For the WhatsApp application, they used several features, namely (1) photos of student answers sheet,

(2) photo of work product, (3) videos, and (4) voice notes. It is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Teacher Assessment Media

Based on the interview results, the platforms used by teachers to carry out assessments are WhatsApp and Google Form. There were 2 respondents who said that the assessment media they used during the Covid-19 Pandemic were WhatsApp and Google Form, namely NYN and YSR. The WhatsApp platform is used in practical assessments and oral tests. There is a Google form for taking written tests. The teachers ask students to fill out a form for both multiple choice questions and essays. Meanwhile, WAS, SNW, AZM, and SDY use the WhatsApp platform for written tests, practical, and oral tests. The way to assess practice is the same as NYN and YSR, namely through photos or videos sent by students. Meanwhile, written assessments are carried out by sharing PDF questions via the WhatsApp platform and asking students to send photos of answer sheets via WhatsApp. Especially for SNW, he also uses the voice note feature for oral tests. Some students also stated that most teachers carry out assessments using WhatsApp. This was conveyed by SNN and HRR students.

Figure 3. Teacher Assessment Media Based on School Geographical Location

Based on the geographic location of the school, the Google Form assessment media is used by teachers in schools both in the city center and in the suburbs. The assessment medium using voice notes is used by teachers at schools in the city center. Meanwhile, the assessment media by sending photos and videos via the WhatsApp application is carried out by teachers at schools in the suburbs. These findings are shown in Figure 3.

Regarding the frequency of teachers carrying out assessments, two pieces of information were obtained. First, there are teachers whose assessment frequency during the Covid-19 Pandemic was the same as before the Covid-19

Pandemic. Meanwhile, there are teachers whose assessment frequency was reduced during the Covid-19 pandemic. If we look at the school geographic location, the frequency of assessments for both schools in the city center and suburbs is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Teacher Assessment Frequency Based on School Geographical Location

SDY and WAS are respondents who reduced their assessment frequency. Meanwhile, respondents who made the same assessment as before the Covid-19 pandemic were NYN, SNW, and YSR. From Figure 4, teachers at schools in the city center carried out assessments during the Covid-19 Pandemic with the same frequency of assessments as before the Covid-19 Pandemic. Meanwhile, for schools on the outskirts of the city, there are schools with the same or reduced frequency.

The Covid-19 pandemic has made all schools switch to an online learning system. This has an impact on the assessment system during the Covid-19 Pandemic. Even though it has been running well, online assessment still has problems. The assessment constraints found in this research include (1) browsing answers on Google, (2) waiting for parents' cell phones to upload, and (3) parents completing assignments. This is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Assessment Problem

Several students at SDY and WAS schools carry out browsing activities for answers to their assignments via the Google search website. This causes teachers to be unable to check students' actual conditions or competencies. Apart from that, the problem experienced was when sending assignments. This is because students must wait for their parents' cell phones to send assignment answers. This results in students being late in uploading answers to teacher

assignments. This is what causes students to have less discipline in answering their assignments.

The final assessment obstacle is the student's assignments carried out by their parents. This obstacle became the main obstacle in assessment during the Covid-19 Pandemic. This is because this obstacle was conveyed by NYN, SNW, SDY, WAS, and YSR. If we look at the geographic location of the school, the assessment constraints for both schools in the city center and on the outskirts of the city are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Assessment Problems Based on School Geographical Location

Figure 6 shows that the tasks carried out by parents are the main obstacle in all schools both in the city center and the suburbs. The problem of waiting for parents' cellphones to upload and students browsing for answers on Google is only found in schools on the outskirts of the city, while schools in the city center are not.

The assessment process carried out by elementary school teachers in the Banyumas District online can be viewed from 3 aspects, namely (1) what assessment media teachers use in online assessments, (2) the frequency with which teachers carry out assessments during the Covid-19 Pandemic, and (3) obstacles emerged during the online assessment during the Covid-19 Pandemic. The assessment media used by teachers in assessment are Google forms and the WhatsApp platform. Google forms are used by teachers to enter questions that are usually printed on paper and then change them into online question form. The questions given can be multiple choice or descriptive. Google Form also has a quiz feature which makes it easy for teachers to get final grades easily. The quiz feature is effective in conducting multiple choice type assessments. Teachers will get grades directly easily. The use of Google forms in conducting assessments is often used by teachers so that there is a lot of research explaining the effectiveness of using Google forms in assessments (Fonseca & Faria, 2021).

The second application used by elementary school teachers in the Banyumas sub-district environment to carry out assessments is WhatsApp. The teacher gathers his students into a WhatsApp group. In the WhatsApp group, teachers give questions or assignments that their students will work on. Collecting student assignments uses WhatsApp features including: (1) uploading photos, (2)

uploading videos, and (3) voice notes. The photo upload feature in WhatsApp is a feature where WhatsApp users can upload photos or images to a WhatsApp group. Students will take photos of the answers to the assignments given by the teacher and then upload them to WhatsApp. The next feature is video upload. The video upload feature has almost the same function as the photo upload feature. The difference is the video upload feature is usually used for assignments that involve student movements or performances. Possible tasks from the video upload feature are memorization tasks and student character assessments. The last feature of WhatsApp that can be used in assessing learning outcomes is the voice note feature. This feature is very suitable for tasks such as memorization. This feature is indeed lower than the video upload feature which can display pictures of students. However, this feature is much lighter in terms of memory capacity used. The use of WhatsApp in conducting assessments is often used by teachers so that many studies explain the effectiveness of using WhatsApp in assessments (Gon & Rawekar, 2017).

Judging from the geographical location of the school, the Google Form assessment media is used by teachers in schools both in the city center and on the outskirts of the city. The assessment medium using voice notes is used by teachers at schools in the city center. Meanwhile, the assessment media by uploading photos and videos via the WhatsApp application is carried out by teachers at schools on the outskirts of the city. This means showing the implication that teachers' ability to use technology in learning is evenly distributed. Equal distribution of teacher abilities across regions is important to improve the quality of education (Siljamäki & Anttila, 2021).

Judging from the frequency of assessment, teachers in conducting assessments are divided into 2 types. First, there are teachers whose assessment frequency during the Covid-19 Pandemic was the same as their assessment frequency before the Covid-19 Pandemic. If we look at the geographic location of schools, teachers at schools in the city center carry out assessments during the Covid-19 Pandemic at the same frequency as their assessment frequency before the Covid-19 Pandemic. Meanwhile, for schools on the outskirts of the city, there are schools with the same or reduced frequency. Reducing the frequency is not a problem because during the Covid-19 Pandemic Indonesia used an emergency education curriculum. The emergency curriculum during the Covid-19 Pandemic was established because during the Covid-19 Pandemic it was not possible to carry out the same learning as before the Covid-19 Pandemic (Marannu, 2021). In the curriculum, it is stated that teachers are allowed to reduce the frequency of assessments and have an obligation to pass all their students.

The next review of the assessment process is the obstacles that emerged during the assessment process during the Covid-19 pandemic. The Covid-19 pandemic has made all schools switch to an online learning system. This has an

impact on the assessment system during the Covid-19 Pandemic. Even though it has been running well, online assessment still has problems. The assessment constraints found in this research include (1) browsing answers on Google, (2) waiting for parents' cell phones to upload, and (3) parents completing assignments. Rapid technological developments can have both positive and negative impacts. Students who carry out browsing activities can see the answers on Google from 2 points of view. From the first point of view, students mean having good technological literacy. From the second point of view, we can state that the student cheated in the assessment process. Technological developments that are not balanced with the strength of their character result in students making the wrong use of developing technology (Peterson, 2020). The next obstacle is waiting for parents' cellphones to upload student assignments. This obstacle is found in students in schools geographically located on the edge of the city. This is because during the learning process, students do not have cellphones/smartphones. Therefore, uneven economic development affects the quality of education (Kraus et al., 2017). The last problem in online assessment is the student assignments. This obstacle arose because the change in the learning system from offline to online resulted in a decrease in students' understanding in lessons (Kristiyani, 2021). This results in students becoming less confident in doing assignments. Therefore, some parents take action to do their children's work.

Use of Criteria in Determining Student Achievement in Online Assessment

The Covid-19 pandemic has turned all assignments into online assignments. This also has an impact on the criteria for assessing student assignments. Even though there are teachers who still use the same assessment criteria as before, teachers are found who give scores based on the time students submit assignments. In summary, these findings are depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Assessment Criteria

The usual way of assessing teachers is the way of assessing teachers like before the pandemic. Most teacher respondents said that they used the usual assessment methods during the Covid-19 pandemic. These findings are

also supported by information from SDY, WAS, and YSR. The results of interviews with SNW and SDY also show that they give additional marks to students who submit on time. This is an assessment method that can only be carried out during the Covid-19 Pandemic. From Figure 7, both teachers in the city center and the suburbs carried out the same assessment methods during the Covid-19 pandemic.

The Covid-19 pandemic has changed all assignments to online assignments. This also has an impact on the way teachers assess student assignments. Even though there are still teachers who still use the usual assessment method, it was also found that there are teachers who do so by considering the timing of students' assignment submissions. If you look at the geographic location of the school, the method of assessing teachers in both schools in the city center and in the suburb uses the same method of assessment during the Covid-19 pandemic. This means the use of criteria in determining student success in online learning activities in both schools in the city center and the suburbs. This method is a method commonly used by teachers as appreciation that students have submitted assignments according to the specified time limit.

Implication of Online Learning Assessment on Education Quality

The research data in the section on the implications of online learning assessment for the quality of education shows 2 findings including: (1) student abilities and (2) student behavior during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Student Ability

Students' abilities in this research were seen from 3 aspects, namely (1) reading ability, (2) writing ability, and (3) numeracy ability.

Table 2. Student ability

Student Ability	Condition
Reading	Decreased
Writing	Decreased and Still Remain
Numeracy	Decreased

The decline in students' ability in reading was expressed by NYN. This information is also in line with information expressed by SNW, SDY, WAS, and YSR that students' reading abilities have also decreased because most school assignments are done by parents. SDY subjects stated that 80% could not read because they were lazy about studying and too often held their cell phones for things that were not useful. The YSR subject stated that children's reading abilities were much reduced due to limited learning time and lack of parental support.

Regarding writing ability, students' writing ability in elementary schools was found in two conditions. There are schools where students' writing abilities decline and there are schools where students' writing abilities remain the same. Four respondents said that students' writing ability

had decreased, namely NYN, SDY, WAS, and YSR. The only respondent who stated that the students' writing skills at their school remained the same was SNW. The SNW subject stated that the students' writing abilities were stable. As for the aspect of numeracy ability, the same thing was found as reading ability. Students' abilities tend to decline in the numeracy aspect. This statement was made by all research respondents.

As for students' feelings and experiences during online assessments, students felt difficulties in learning during the pandemic. The following statement from MIR and GIS stated that they were nervous because they did not understand the material. From this description, it can be concluded that there is an aspect of reading ability, all students at the school that was used as the research object experienced a decline. Regarding writing ability, it was found that some students' writing ability decreased and some remained constant. Like reading ability, students' ability in the numeracy aspect also decreases.

Student Behavior

Most respondents in this study said that the Covid-19 pandemic had a negative impact on student behavior. The results of this research show that there are at least 5 negative student behaviors that emerged because of the Covid-19 Pandemic. These five behaviors are (1) lack of responsibility, (2) lack of discipline, (3) lack of independence, (4) lack of politeness, and (5) lazy to study. This is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Student Behavior

The first negative behavior is lack of responsibility. The students are less responsible for the tasks given by the teacher. This was stated by SNW, SDY, and YSR. During the pandemic, most of the tasks were done by parents. Children become lazy and irresponsible in their duties. Apart from that, students are more indifferent to school assignments. The results of interviews with YSR also provide information that students also have less independent behavior towards their assignments. The next student's behavior is impolite. This was stated by SNW that student behavior during the pandemic was not good, and politeness also decreased.

Another negative student behavior that emerged after the pandemic was being lazy about studying. This was stated by SNW and WAS. This causes 80% to be less able to read, count and write. The final student behavior is lack of discipline. Information was said by all respondents. One example is that when there is an assignment, not all students have completed it, many students submit assignments via video or photo or Google Form which are late and exceed the specified limit.

If we look at the geographical location of the school, the behavior of students at both schools in the city center and on the outskirts of the city is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Student Behavior Based on School Geographical Location

From Figure 9, irresponsible behavior, lack of discipline, and laziness in studying appear among students in both schools in the city center and on the outskirts of the city. Disrespectful behavior appears in students at schools in the city center, while less independent behavior appears in students at schools on the outskirts of the city.

The review of implications in this research is the implications for cognitive and affective learning outcomes. From a cognitive perspective, students' abilities are seen from their ability to read, write and calculate. These three abilities are basic abilities that elementary school children must have. The Indonesian government has focused this capability into a national program, namely CALISTUNG (Read, Write, Count) (Rachman, 2019). In the aspect of reading ability, all students in the schools that were used as research objects experienced a decline. Likewise with the aspect of calculating ability. Meanwhile, regarding writing ability, it was found that there were schools where students' writing ability had decreased and some had remained the same. The Covid-19 pandemic has caused the quality of learning to decline so that this has an impact on students' reading, writing and numeracy abilities (Hasanah et al., 2022).

From an affective aspect, most respondents in this study said that the Covid-19 pandemic had a negative impact on student behavior. The results of this research show that there are at least 5 negative student behaviors that emerged because of the Covid-19 Pandemic. These five behaviors are (1) lack of responsibility, (2) lack of discipline, (3) lack of autonomy, (4) lack of politeness, and (5) laziness in studying. Responsible behavior is the behavior of students who do not carry out their duties as

students well. This could be due to the absence of direct learning interaction. Teachers still have difficulty creating classes that use virtual meeting applications such as Zoom Meeting and Google Meet. Therefore, students did not understand the material well during the Covid-19 Pandemic. Good use of virtual classes can actually still maintain students' abilities (Malkawi et al., 2021).

Lack of discipline is the behavior of students not submitting their assignments on time. This behavior arises because during the learning process, students do not have cellphones/smartphones. Therefore, uneven economic development affects the quality of education (Kraus et al., 2017). The next behavior is lack of independence. The family is a means of informal education (Smith & Seal, 2021). However, parents doing their children's work is not a reflection of the implementation of the family as a means of informal education. This has the impact of less independent behavior on students.

Disrespectful behavior appears in learning activities via WhatsApp groups. Disrespectful behavior here is the behavior of students using inappropriate emoticons and sticker features during the learning process. This is because difficulties in applying character in the learning process can result in students behaving impolitely (Wua et al., 2022). The last behavior is being lazy about studying. The change in the education system to a zoning system means that students whose homes are close to the school are more likely to be accepted than students whose homes are further away. The effect of this system coupled with the implementation of an emergency curriculum where teachers must graduate all their students can give the idea that students do not need to study to graduate or get a good school. Therefore, these two reasons can have the effect of lazy behavior on students.

CONCLUSION

From the discussion of the research results, it can be concluded that: (1) the types of assessment used in the assessment are multiple choice, multiple choice, description and practice and oral, (2) the assessment planning process consists of three parts; media (GF, Whatsap), some frequencies are the same or less, and obstacles (waiting for parents' cell phones) in assessment, (3) there are the same learning assessment criteria and some give added value to those who submit on time, and (4) The implication of online learning assessment is that the average ability decreases (for example in reading, writing, and arithmetic), and behavioral attitudes also decrease.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

All authors contribute equally to any part of the research; this is an agreed-upon joint project.

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